

Searching Pattern of Users of Online Public Access Catalogues for Retrieval of Bengali Documents in the University Libraries of West Bengal

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This paper covers a use study of the Online Public Access Catalogues (OPACs) at University Libraries of West Bengal. Highlights the subject access for Bengali documents in OPACs. Finds that most of the users are postgraduate students and that the majority of users are male. Result reveals that search experience using subject headings is not satisfactory. Keywords search rather performs better but due to redundancy of search, it is hard to retrieve required documents in least possible time. It is also revealed that fewer perform known-items searches and their success rates for these searches are generally good. Thus, the findings demand a standardized and uniform vocabulary control device for making subject headings for Bengali documents in OPACs.

Keywords: Bengali Documents, OPAC, Subject Headings, Online Catalogue

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1 Introduction

Nowadays libraries are gradually transforming by use of ICT based tools and techniques. Using Integrated Library Management Software (ILMS), libraries can perform technical as well as administrative jobs. Although at present some of the libraries are running with manual and automated systems simultaneously, some of them have already terminated the dual system. Library catalogue is the surrogate of entire collection available in a library. Subject catalogue has an important role to satisfy the unknown document approach, i.e. subject approach of user community. Study of literature reveals that there are more than 4000

titles published annually in Bengali language from West Bengal. University libraries in West Bengal are found to collect these Bengali language publications. Organization of these publications is a huge task to the University libraries. However, moving from traditional card catalogue to modern Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) has not made subject searching more attractive and effective (Sridhar, 2004). In these circumstances, it has become essential to study the details of use of Bengali subject headings in OPACs in the university libraries of West Bengal.

2 Objective

This study makes an endeavour to assess the use of Bengali subject headings in OPACs in the university libraries of West Bengal. However, to achieve the objective, this study attempts to accomplish the tasks listed hereinunder:

1. To assess the characteristics of the online catalog users;
2. To examine the use of OPACs for retrieving documents;
3. To determine and identify the search pattern for retrieving documents in OPACs as well as their success rate; and
4. To assess the attitude of the users towards the effectiveness of subject headings of Bengali documents in OPACs.

3 Review of Literature

There are so many vocabulary control devices for assigning subject headings in library catalogue, such as the Library of Congress Subject Headings, Sears' List of Subject Headings, MeSH, etc. But, all these devices are used for English language only. Applicability and suitability of their principles in Bengali language may be investigated for proper use. Some problems are associated with Bengali subject headings, because of their semantic and syntax, synonym and homonym, etc. Few initiatives have been made for compiling uniform Subject Headings List in Bengali, but a comprehensive Subject Headings List based on sound principles and rules is yet to be published in Bengali. A pioneer attempt in compiling "Bisay Shironam", a Bengali Subject Headings List, was made by Krishnamay Bhattacharyay (1370), but it is not up-to-date. Another work in Bengali entitled "Bijnan: Bishay Shironam" by Pinaki Nath Mukhopadhyay was published in 2001. Mukhopadhyay has prepared a Subject Headings List on the subject science only. Besides, Ratna Bandyapadhyay

wrote a book entitled "Bishay Shironam Gathan Paddhati: darshan, sahitya, shilpakala" in 2004. Bandyapadhyay (2001) finds that in the present era, rate of publication of Bengali documents is growing and collection of those Bengali books, journals, etc. is increasing. But many of the libraries lack the subject catalogue. Where ever Bengali subject headings are assigned, are not complete or proper and these also lack standardized principles. Due to unavailability of standard Bengali subject headings, users' approaches are not satisfied. Bandyapadhyay studied different public libraries in West Bengal and Bangladesh and finally felt the necessity to prepare a Subject Headings List in Bengali language. In this context some of the publications in Bengali such as National Bibliography: Bengali; Kraylabhya Bangla Granther Bishayanug Talika (Bengali Trade Bibliography Arranged according to Subject); Books in Print and Calcutta Book Fair Directory; Bani Basu's Bangla Shishu Sahityer Granthapanji (Bibliography of Bengali Children Literature); Probhat Kumar Mukhopadhyay's Bangla granthaborgikaran (Scheme of Bengali book Classification); Ramkrishna Saha's Bangla Pustak Bargikaran (Bengali Book Classification) should be mentioned. Studies on use of OPACs are plenty and there exists good number of reviews of OPAC studies (Larson, 1991; Hildreth, 1985; O'Brien, 1994). Because of lack of uniform Bengali Subject Headings List, subject access is most problematic and difficult in OPACs.

4 Methodology

In order to achieve the objective of this study, it has been intended to adopt survey method. However, the population in respect of this study is large. Therefore, for convenience, it was intended to carry out a sample study of OPACs of four university libraries out of which two libraries from urban areas, and the other two libraries from sub-urban or rural areas in West Bengal were selected, i.e. University of Calcutta Library, Jadavpur University Library, University of Kalyani Library, and Vidyasagar University Library. A structured schedule (*vide* Annexure) was prepared to record data through systematic study and observation of the use of subject headings of Bengali documents in OPACs. With a view to enhance the validity and reliability of the schedule, experts in the field of Library Science, Psychology and Statistics were consulted and requested to review the schedule critically. Then the schedule was revised based on the suggestions given by the experts. A total of 800 schedules (200 for each of the selected university library) were distributed to record the primary data, out of which 680 (85 percent)

schedules were received till the end of data collection. Besides these, relevant data were collected from observation of the libraries, and their annual reports, etc. Quantitative data collected in the above manner were analyzed, using descriptive statistics, classified, tabulated, compared and interpreted duly keeping in view the objective of the investigation.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 User Characteristics

To determine the characteristics of the users, it was found (Table 1) that most of the OPAC users were postgraduate students (55 percent). Besides 25.29 percent were undergraduate students followed by 9.85 percent were doctoral students, 7.21 percent were faculty members, while remaining 2.65 percent did not expose their status.

Table 1: Status of the Users

Status	User	Percentage (%)
Undergraduate Students	172	25.29
Postgraduate Students	374	55.00
Doctoral Students	67	9.85
Faculty Members	49	7.21
Unspecified	18	2.65
Total	680	100

In respect of sex, the result of the study (Table 2) indicated that most of the OPAC users were male (57.06 percent). Besides 37.94 percent identified themselves as female, and remaining 5 percent did not indicate their sex.

Table 2: Sex of the Users

Sex	User	Percentage (%)
Male	388	57.06
Female	258	37.94
Unspecified	34	5.00
Total	680	100.00

With regard to the trend of search experience of the users, it was found (Table 3) that maximum (48.38 percent) of the respondents had been using library OPAC for five or more times per week. Besides 23.38 percent had been using the OPAC for 2-4 times per month followed by 12.50 percent had been using 2 to 4 times per week, and 10.74 percent had been using less than 6 times per year. Rest 5 percent did never get access to OPAC to search their required documents.

Table 3: Frequency of the Use of OPAC

Frequency	User	Percentage (%)
5 or more times per week	329	48.38
2 to 4 times per week	85	12.50
2 to 4 times per month	159	23.38
Less than 6 times per year	73	10.74
Never	34	5.00
Total	680	100.00

5.2 Search Pattern

With regard to search pattern of users in OPACs, it was found (Figure 1) that maximum search approach for known items was title search, i.e. 17.35 percent users preferred to search documents by their titles. Besides 13.82 percent users preferred search by author, but combined search (14.56 percent) of author and title was little higher than author search. Altogether, known-items search were 45.73 percent of the total number of searches performed.

Figure 1: Search Approaches in OPACs

Searching by Subject Headings was 29.12 percent of the total search approach, which was highest among all search approaches. Besides 25.15 percent search was found to be done by keywords. Therefore a large number of users' approach in OPACs were either by subject headings or by user defined keywords, i.e. unknown items search. Altogether, unknown-items search was 54.27 percent of the total number of searches performed.

5.3 Document Retrieval

The results of searches by subjects and by keywords were compared. For subject searches, 42.50 percent got zero result, 30.44 percent got 1-100 results, 20 percent got 100-499 results, and 7.06 percent got 500 or more results. For keyword searches, 8.97 percent got zero result, 25.74 percent got 1-100 results, 31.76 percent got 100-499 results, and 33.53 percent got 500 or more results (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Rate of Document Retrieval in OPACs

5.4 Impact of Zero Search Result

When search result was zero, 61.18 percent respondents changed search terms, 25.88 percent took suggestions from OPACs, and 12.94 percent went back to the search terms already used (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Modification of Search Terms when Search Results is Zero

5.5 Satisfaction Level of the Users

Level of satisfaction of the users in search process was tried to uncover. Respondents were asked to point out marks in five point scale, i.e. Very Unsatisfied-> 1 2 3 4 5 <-Very Satisfied. Result indicated that search experience using Subject Headings was not satisfactory, as only 12.35 percent respondents were satisfied with this process. Rather keywords search technique was often used to obtain required document and only 9.85 percent respondents were found least satisfied with this process. Combining search by Subject Headings and Keywords was average used technique; 24.26 percent users had given 4 marks out of 5 and 23.68 percent users had given 3 marks out of 5. Simultaneously 16.03 percent users were found least satisfied, and 16.62 percent users were found happiest with this search experience (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Comparison of Satisfaction Level of the Users

6 Conclusion

The study reveals that OPAC is one of the useful tools for searching documents in the library. Maximum users (48.38 percent) use it five or more times per week, whereas 12.50 percent users use it 2-4 times in a week. Functionality of OPAC needs to be improved to provide more user-friendly services. Providing access points by subject headings should be a major consideration for satisfying users' approach. Result indicates that search experience using subject headings is not satisfactory, as only 12.35 percent users are satisfied with this process. Keywords search rather perform better, but due to redundancy of search, it is hard to retrieve required documents in least possible time. Subject headings need to be consistently standardized and each record should contain both broader terms and narrower terms to balance the recall and precision of search results. Finally, the outcome of this study demands a standardized and uniform vocabulary control device for making subject headings for Bengali documents in OPACs.

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Annexure : Schedule for Survey of Users

This survey is intended to investigate the usability of Bengali Subject Headings in library Online Public Access Catalogues.

1. University Status (Please check one)

- a) Undergraduate Student b) Master Student
 c) Doctoral Student d) Post-Doctoral Student
 e) Faculty f) Other

2. Gender (Check one)

- a) Male b) Female

3. Years of Computer Experience (Please check one)

- a) < 1 Year b) 1-2 Years c) 2-3 Years d) 3-5 Years
 e) > 5 Years

4. Years of Database Searching Experience (Please check one)

- a) < 1 Year b) 1-2 Years c) 2-3 Years d) 3-5 Years
 e) > 5 Years

5. What kinds of database you usually use?

6. How often do you use Database for searching?

7. Experience using library catalogs (Please check one)

- a) 5 or more times per week
 b) 2 to 4 times per week
 c) 2 times per month
 d) Less than 6 times per year
 e) Never

8. What methods you generally use to find out required document?

- a) Keywords search
 b) Title search
 c) Author search
 d) Subject search
 e) Combined search

9. Before this search experiment, did you understand or feel familiar with keyword or subject headings terminology?

10. Before this search experiment, have you ever used keyword and/or subject headings for your search?

Yes No

If so, which (Please check one)?

- a) Keyword only b) Subject Headings only c) Both

11. After this search experiment, what is your preference for search? (Please check one)

- a) Keyword only b) Subject Headings only c) Combining both

12. Compare the three search sessions when you answer the following questions:

A. Keyword search

- (1) How satisfied were you with finding the information you sought? On a scale of 1-5, how easy was it to find the book? (Please circle one)
 Very Unsatisfied-> 1 2 3 4 5 <-Very Satisfied
 (2) Please list the reasons why you gave the answer

(3) How satisfied were you with search process? (Please circle one)

Very Unsatisfied-> 1 2 3 4 5 <-Very Satisfied

(4) Please list the reasons why you gave the answer

B. Subject Headings Search

- (1) How satisfied were you with finding the information you sought? On a scale of 1-5, how easy was it to find the book? (Please circle one)
 Very Unsatisfied-> 1 2 3 4 5 <-Very Satisfied
 (2) Please list the reasons why you gave the answer

(3) How satisfied were you with search process? (Please circle one)

Very Unsatisfied-> 1 2 3 4 5 <-Very Satisfied

(4) Please list the reasons why you gave the answer

C. Combining Search

- (1) How satisfied were you with finding the information you sought? On a scale of 1-5, how easy was it to find the book? (Please circle one)
 Very Unsatisfied-> 1 2 3 4 5 <-Very Satisfied
 (2) Please list the reasons why you gave the answer

(3) How satisfied were you with search process? (Please circle one)

Very Unsatisfied-> 1 2 3 4 5 <-Very Satisfied

(4) Please list the reasons why you gave the answer

13. How do you search subject headings or keywords which are in languages written in non-Roman script?

	Search in English or Romanization.	Search in the original non-Roman script.	Search both
Subject	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Headings			
Keywords	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

14. How you adjust search terms when search results are zero

- a) Change search terms
 b) Select subject term from alphabetic
 c) Select subject term from retrieved item

15. How do you find searching the OPAC by controlled Headings?

On a scale of 1-5, how easy was it to find the book? (Please circle one)
 Very Unsatisfied-> 1 2 3 4 5 <-Very Satisfied

16. What are some difficulties you encounter when you search Bengali items by controlled English subject access? Choose all that apply.

- a) I usually don't find what I want:
 b) I don't know the English equivalent:
 c) The Romanization of a term in the English
 subject headings is not known to me
 d) Others

17. Do you find that the presence of controlled English subject headings in bibliographic records helps you find and identify the Bengali items you need?

On a scale of 1-5, how easy was it to find the book? (Please circle one)
 Very Unsatisfied-> 1 2 3 4 5 <-Very Satisfied

18. Do you think it would be useful to add subject searching capability in Bengali language to the library OPAC?

- a) Yes
 b) No
 c) Not

19. Do you think it is a good idea to make a library catalog open for end user tagging?

- a) Yes
 b) No
 c) Not

20. List your favorite ideas or suggestions to improve non-English subject access in library online catalog.

Thank you for assisting in this study. Your responses will help to assess the details of the use of university library OPACs and subject searching for library resources.